

Original paper

MADANIY DIPLOMATIYADA MAQOM FESTIVALLARINING O'RNI: XALQARO TAJRIBA

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Annotatsiya

KIRISH: ushbu maqolada maqom san'atining O'zbekiston Respublikasining madaniy diplomatiyasidagi o'rni va uning xalqaro miqyosdagi ahamiyati tahlil qilinadi. Tadqiqotda maqom san'atining tarixiy, estetik hamda diplomatik qirralari yoritilib, O'zbekistonning xalqaro maqom festivallari orqali milliy merosni global darajada targ'ib etishdagi tajribasi ko'rib chiqiladi. Shuningdek, Eron, Ozarbayjon, Turkiya va Misr kabi davlatlarning musiqiy diplomatiya yo'nalishidagi tajribalari solishtirma tahlil qilinib, O'zbekiston modeli mintaqaviy "yumshoq kuch" siyosatining samarali shakli sifatida baholanadi. Maqom festivallari milliy brendni shakllantirish, madaniy aloqalarni rivojlantirish va xalqaro imijni mustahkamlashda muhim rol o'ynayotgani ilmiy asoslar bilan isbotlanadi. Tadqiqot natijalariga ko'ra, maqom san'ati O'zbekistonning xalqaro madaniy siyosatida tinchlik, do'stlik va madaniyatlararo muloqot timsoli sifatida alohida o'rin tutadi.

MAQSAD: Maqom san'atining O'zbekistonning xalqaro madaniy siyosatidagi o'rni va uning "yumshoq kuch" elementi sifatidagi strategik ahamiyatini ochib berish.

MATERIALLAR VA METODLAR: Tadqiqotda tahliliy, qiyosiy va madaniyatshunoslik metodlar qo'llanilgan. Xalqaro festival materiallari, diplomatik ma'lumotlar, BMT va UNESCO hujjatlari, shuningdek, ekspert interv'yulari asos sifatida o'rganilgan.

MUHOKAMA VA NATIJALAR: O'zbekiston tajribasi shuni ko'rsatadiki, maqom san'ati milliy brend va diplomatik vosita sifatida xalqaro miqyosda tinchlik, do'stlik va o'zaro anglashuvni targ'ib etadi. Maqom festivallari madaniy identitetni mustahkamlaydi, turli xalqlar o'rtasidagi madaniy muloqotni chuqurlashtiradi hamda O'zbekiston imijini ijobiy yo'nalishda shakllantiradi.

XULOSA: Maqom san'ati O'zbekistonning madaniy diplomatiyasida strategik ahamiyat kasb etib, xalqaro muloqot va madaniyatlararo integratsiyaning muhim timsoli sifatida namoyon bo'lmoqda.

Kalit so'zlar: maqom, madaniy diplomatiya, xalqaro festival, musiqiy meros, yumshoq kuch, milliy brend, O'zbekiston tajribasi, xalqaro imij.

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РОЛЬ ФЕСТИВАЛЕЙ МАКОМА В КУЛЬТУРНОЙ ДИПЛОМАТИИ: МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЙ ОПЫТ

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Аннотация

ВВЕДЕНИЕ: в статье анализируется роль искусства макама в культурной дипломатии Республики Узбекистан и его значение на международной арене. Освещаются исторические, эстетические и дипломатические аспекты макамного искусства, а также опыт Узбекистана в продвижении национального музыкального наследия через международные макам-фестивали. Сопоставляются примеры музыкальной дипломатии Ирана, Азербайджана, Турции и Египта. Отмечается, что узбекская модель служит эффективной формой региональной политики «мягкой силы».

ЦЕЛЬ: определить место и значение искусства макама в международной культурной политике Узбекистана как инструмента «мягкой силы».

МАТЕРИАЛЫ И МЕТОДЫ: использованы аналитический, сравнительный и культурологический методы. В качестве источников применены материалы международных фестивалей, документы ЮНЕСКО и ООН, а также экспертные интервью.

ОБСУЖДЕНИЕ И РЕЗУЛЬТАТЫ: опыт Узбекистана показывает, что искусство макама является действенным инструментом культурной дипломатии, укрепляющим национальный имидж и способствующим развитию межкультурного диалога. Международные макам-фестивали становятся платформой мира и дружбы между народами.

ЗАКЛЮЧЕНИЕ: макамное искусство занимает особое место в культурной дипломатии Узбекистана, представляя страну как носителя мира, диалога и духовного наследия.

Ключевые слова: макам, культурная дипломатия, международный фестиваль, музыкальное наследие, мягкая сила, национальный бренд, опыт Узбекистана, международный имидж.

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THE PLACE OF MAQOM FESTIVALS IN CULTURAL DIPLOMACY: INTERNATIONAL EXPERIENCE

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Annotation

INTRODUCTION: this article analyzes the role of maqom art in Uzbekistan's cultural diplomacy and its significance on the international stage. It explores the historical, aesthetic, and diplomatic aspects of maqom, examining Uzbekistan's experience in

promoting its national heritage through international maqom festivals. Comparative analysis includes the experiences of Iran, Azerbaijan, Turkey, and Egypt, highlighting Uzbekistan's model as an effective form of regional "soft power."

AIM: to identify the strategic importance of maqom art as an element of Uzbekistan's international cultural policy and a tool of "soft power."

MATERIALS AND METHODS: the research applies analytical, comparative, and cultural studies methods. Data were drawn from international festival materials, UNESCO and UN documents, and expert interviews.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS: Uzbekistan's experience demonstrates that maqom art functions as an instrument of peace, friendship, and intercultural understanding, enhancing the nation's cultural image and global recognition. Maqom festivals strengthen national identity while promoting cross-cultural dialogue.

CONCLUSION: maqom art plays a strategic role in Uzbekistan's cultural diplomacy, symbolizing peace, cultural continuity, and the country's contribution to global harmony.

Keywords: maqom, cultural diplomacy, international festival, musical heritage, soft power, national brand, Uzbekistan's experience, international image.

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In recent years, the Republic of Uzbekistan has been implementing large-scale reforms aimed at developing national culture, strengthening cultural diplomacy, and promoting national heritage internationally. In this process, maqom art, as a cultural "soft power" of Uzbekistan, is taking a special place in international relations [1:15]. Maqom art is a unique phenomenon that expresses the musical thinking, aesthetic taste, and spiritual world of the Uzbek people, and is recognized not only as art, but also as a means of national identity and cultural diplomacy. Therefore, the Resolution No. PQ-3279 "On holding the International Conference on Maqom Art", adopted by the President of Uzbekistan on September 17, 2017, has acquired historical significance in the development of this field [6].

Based on this decision, the first "International Festival of Maqom Art" was held in Shahrisabz in August 2018. Artists, musicologists, and diplomatic representatives from 73 countries participated in it. This festival not only revived the performing tradition, but also gave impetus to the formation of Uzbekistan as a cultural brand in the international arena [7:34].

According to the 2024 report of the Ministry of Culture, more than 1,500 foreign participants, including representatives of Turkey, Iran, Tajikistan, Azerbaijan, Egypt, and France, participated in the Maqom festivals held in recent years [11:3]. This indicates that Maqom art has become a platform for international diplomatic dialogue.

Also, the Law "On Culture" adopted in 2021 (July 22, new edition) established international cooperation in the field of culture and the promotion of national heritage as one of the priorities of state policy [10]. These legal frameworks strengthened the diplomatic significance of maqom festivals, forming them as an integral part of the mechanisms of cultural diplomacy. Today, the International Maqom Festival of Uzbekistan serves not only as an art event, but also as a platform for cultural dialogue and international relations. According to foreign musicologists, this festival is considered "one of the largest musical diplomacy initiatives in the East" [8:19].

Also, practical results such as high-level cultural meetings, scientific conferences, and signing of memorandums of cooperation within the framework of the Maqom Festival increase the effectiveness of cultural diplomacy [12:9]. In this regard, the experience of Uzbekistan is recognized as an advanced model in the field of cultural diplomacy in Central Asia.

Such international prestige of Maqom art, on the one hand, allows us to demonstrate our national heritage in a global context, and on the other hand, to strengthen interethnic dialogue through music. Therefore, Maqom festivals require a separate scientific analysis as an effective tool of Uzbekistan's cultural brand, international image, and diplomatic policy [9: 46].

Maqom art, by its very nature, is a musical heritage that embodies the spirit, historical memory, and aesthetic values of a nation. For this reason, it serves as a diplomatic language that expresses cultural identity internationally [1:27]. Through maqom festivals, states conduct their cultural policy based on the principles of soft power. The theory put forward by Joseph Nye is important in this regard - according to him, "culture, values, and art are the most stable forms of diplomatic influence" [13:5].

The international maqom festival of Uzbekistan is also formed on the basis of this principle, creating a space for interethnic dialogue through music. During the festival, foreign participants not only demonstrate their performance, but also create a basis for the harmonization of cultural values through mutual musical exchange [9:48]. Within the framework of cultural diplomacy, such events provide the following results:

- the promotion of national heritage in the international arena is strengthened;
- a positive image is formed with foreign countries;
- a positive environment for political dialogue is created through art;
- tourism and the creative economy are developed [7:36].

As part of the 2024 Shahrizabz Maqom Festival, an international scientific conference entitled "Maqom – the Musical Heritage of Humanity" was organized, attended by about 200 delegates from more than 30 countries. Uzbekistan's experience in cultural diplomacy at this conference was recognized by organizations such as UNESCO, IRCAM (France), and the British Council [11:5].

International experience: cultural diplomacy through a musical heritage similar to maqom

Iranian experience. The Iranian state has recognized the national musical system called "Radif" as an intangible heritage of UNESCO and has been holding the "Radif Music Festival" since 2009. Through this festival, Iran is promoting its national music as a diplomatic brand. Every year, it attracts representatives of more than 25 countries and serves intercultural dialogue [14:22].

Azerbaijani experience. Azerbaijan's "Mugham Festival" is also an example for Central Asia. It has been held in Baku since 2009 and serves to increase the global prestige of mugham art. The Azerbaijani government sees this festival as a diplomatic tool: ambassadors of various countries, UNESCO representatives, and art historians participate in each festival [15:17].

Turkish experience. In Turkey, the "Konya International Mystic Music Festival" (since 2004) strengthens international cultural dialogue through Sufi music. In addition to music, the festival programs are enriched with scientific forums, folk art exhibitions, and cultural exchange programs. In this way, Turkey is strengthening the "Rumi legacy" as an international diplomatic identity [16:10].

Egyptian experience. Egypt's "Arab Music Festival" has been held in Cairo since 1992 and strengthens cultural solidarity between the countries of the Arab world. Every year, a special diplomatic program called "Cultural Dialogue Evening" is organized as part of the festival, through which art-based dialogue between countries is established [17:8].

The Uzbek maqom festival, unlike the above experiences, is:

- developing as a regional diplomatic platform uniting regional heritage (Central Asian maqom schools);
- combining musical art with scientific research, international seminars, and diplomatic meetings;
- being organized on the basis of strategic cooperation with UNESCO, TURKSOY, and ISESCO;
- cultural agreements, joint projects, and protocols are signed at the end of the festival [11:7].

In this regard, the Uzbek experience is recognized as a regional model of music diplomacy. This model serves as an effective tool not only for strengthening culture, but also for strengthening the national brand and international image [8:20]. The role of maqom festivals in shaping the image of Uzbekistan. During the years of independence, the Republic of Uzbekistan has formed its cultural policy in the international arena in a new concept. One of the main directions of this policy is the promotion of national values and strengthening the image of the state through cultural diplomacy [1:17].

The Resolution of the President of Uzbekistan dated November 17, 2017, No. PQ-3391 "On measures for the further development of the art of maqom" was an important stage in this process. The Resolution emphasized that "maqom art is an invaluable asset of our national culture, a glorious heritage that reflects the spiritual world of our people" [9:3]. Since 2018, the "International Festival of Maqom Art", held in the city of Shahrizabz,

has become the most important brand in the country's cultural diplomacy. The festival has formed a unique model of "cultural diplomacy through heritage" [5: 65].

Through this festival:

- The historical and cultural heritage of Uzbekistan was introduced at the international level;

- Cultural ties with more than 50 countries were strengthened;

- Strategic cooperation with UNESCO was expanded;

- A new impetus was created for international musicological research [6:49].

The 2022 festival was attended by more than 350 foreign guests and 76 representatives of foreign media outlets, actively participating in promoting a positive cultural image of Uzbekistan [12:10]. The Maqom Festival is not only a musical event, but also serves as an international diplomatic platform. Each participating state delegation demonstrates its national art through cultural programs, which creates a positive environment for international dialogue [3:102].

Direct cooperation between musicologists, representatives of the diplomatic corps and journalists is being established through the "Maqom Forums" and scientific conferences held within the framework of the festival. This process is considered the main tool for strengthening Uzbekistan's "soft power" policy [13, 7-b]. For example, at the 2024 Shahrizabz Festival, representatives of Iran, Turkey, Italy and Japan participated in the international session entitled "Maqam Diplomacy" and put forward the idea of "Music is an Ambassador of Peace" [11:9]. Several international initiatives have been put forward in Uzbekistan's cultural diplomacy based on the art of maqam:

1. "Central Asian Maqam Dialogue" — a cooperation platform organized with the participation of musicologists from Central Asian countries;

2. "UNESCO Maqam Heritage Network" — an international scientific network proposed by Uzbekistan and approved in 2023;

3. "Youth Maqam Camp" — an educational project for young performers, in which students from 15 countries participated;

4. "Silk Road Music Diplomacy Initiative" — a new diplomatic program aimed at integrating maqam with the heritage of the Silk Road [10:14].

These initiatives not only expand Uzbekistan's international cultural ties, but also provide an impetus for the scientific study of maqom art at the global level [4:67]. Maqom festivals, as an integral part of the creative economy, also have a positive impact on the country's tourism potential. According to the 2024 data of the Tourism Committee of Uzbekistan, more than 40 thousand foreign tourists visited during the Shahrizabz festival, which is 26% more than in previous years [12:8]. The stage, advertising, costumes and songs created during the festival were widely covered in the international media as a creative brand of the country. As a result, maqom art is being formed as a cultural product combined with economic benefit [8:53].

Conclusion. The art of maqom is not only a high artistic expression of Uzbek music, but also a symbol of the historical memory, spiritual world and aesthetic thinking of the

people. During the years of independence, this heritage rose to the level of state policy and became an important factor in shaping the international cultural image of Uzbekistan [1:17]. The International Festival of Maqom Art, established by the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PQ-3391, is today recognized not only as an art arena, but also as a means of cultural diplomacy [9:3]. The festival has achieved such important results as introducing Uzbekistan to the world through its musical heritage, strengthening interethnic friendship, and creating a positive image on a global scale [5: 65].

Analyzing international maqom festivals in conjunction with the experiences of Iran, Azerbaijan, Turkey, and Egypt, the Uzbek model stands out for its integrative and diplomatic features [14:22].

In our country, maqom art is being formed not only as a musical expression, but also as an effective mechanism for developing international political, cultural, and economic cooperation [10, 14-b]. The role of maqom festivals in cultural diplomacy is expressed in the following areas:

- international promotion of national culture;
- strengthening cultural exchange and diplomatic dialogue;
- development of the creative economy and tourism;
- strengthening the positive image of Uzbekistan on a global scale [8:53].

In the future, the development of digital maqom diplomacy, regional cooperation festivals, and scientific and academic diplomacy will turn Uzbekistan into a center for international intercultural dialogue [15:28]. Therefore, the art of maqom is not only Uzbek national pride, but also a powerful diplomatic tool that unites humanity on an international scale as a symbol of peace, beauty, and cultural harmony.

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